

Automated Detection of Tricuspid Regurgitation Using Multiple Instance Learning on Doppler Echocardiograms

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Introduction/Background

Tricuspid regurgitation (TR) affects >70 million people worldwide. 36% of patients with severe-TR die within 1 year, however >90% of these patients are not intervened upon due to prohibitive surgical mortality. Early diagnosis of severe TR is critical for treatment effectiveness, but such diagnoses are time-consuming and require expert image acquisition and interpretation of echocardiograms (echo). Thus, there is a critical need for an accurate and rapid method for binary severe-TR (i.e. intervention needed) detection. While 3D Convolutional Neural Networks are frequently used for medical image classification, the variable spatial and temporal dimension sizes of echoes make them less effective and interpretable. Herein we describe an interpretable multiple-instance model to detect severe-TR from echo.

Methods/Intervention

Echocardiograms were interpreted and labeled at the video level by expert cardiologists. Sample gates were extracted and split with a train-validation ratio of 4:1. The multiple-instance model comprises a feature extractor utilizing spatial grouped-convolution blocks and two temporal heads, an instance predictor employing a perceptron model, and an instance aggregator using mean-pooling. The pipeline and model architecture are illustrated in Figure 1. A grid-search over hyperparameters was performed for optimization.

Results/Outcome

In total, 3604 echoes were collected (Table 1a). Table 1b shows optimized hyperparameters. Our model achieved a maximum validation accuracy of 81.3% and ROC AUC of 0.865 (Figure 2a, 2b, 2c). Activations of spatial convolutions were used to visualize spatial focus (Figure 2d), and instance predictions were used to identify temporal model focus (Figure 2e).

Conclusion

Our model accurately detects severe-TR from echocardiograms with similar sensitivity and specificity, indicating balanced training. The separation of temporal and spatial features enhances its explainability. Activation of spatial convolutions demonstrate the model's ability to discern cardiac structure and Doppler flow, while single-instance predictions reveal its capability to learn fine-grain features from coarse video-level labels.

Statement of Impact

Our algorithm provides real-time interpretation of echo for severe-TR diagnoses with high sensitivity, allows cardiologists to focus on more severe patient cases, where quick diagnostic turnaround time is critical for intervention efficacy.

Figures

Table 1a. Data Statistics	
Total # of Echocardiograms	3604
Positive (Severe-TR) Samples	1680
Negative (not severe-TR) Samples	1924
Average Frames per Sample (Standard Deviation)	45.6 (16.2)

Table 1b. Model Parameters	
Loss function	Binary Cross Entropy (frame-wise, video-label propagated over frames)
Batch size	1
Optimizer	Stochastic Gradient Descent
Momentum	0.9
Learning Rate	0.01
L2 Normalization	1E-3
Learning Rate Step Schedule	20 epochs, gamma=0.9

Table 1a: Data Statistics. All data were collected from the Cardiology Department at UCI Health. Data were anonymized according to HIPAA standards. Table 1b: Hyperparameters of model. Variable input lengths necessitate a batch size of one, prompting the use of instance normalization over batch normalization.

Figure 1a: overall algorithm pipeline. Echo data has its sample gate extracted using image processing techniques then resampled over the x-y spatial plane. Temporal dimension was left intact to maintain temporal fidelity and preserve temporal correlations. The trained model can accept video echocardiogram inputs of any shape and size, so long as there is enough GPU memory. Figure 1b: architecture of Multiple Instance Model. Dropout layers were employed after spatial convolution blocks 5-7 and after temporal attention heads to decrease overfitting.

Figure 2a: Multiple instance model performance. The left and right sides show loss accuracies over time. Early stopping was employed once the training and validation loss gap becomes too high (validation loss not shown). Figure 2b: confusion matrix for severe Tricuspid Regurgitation detection. Percentages are shown. Figure 2c: Receiver Operating Characteristic curve is shown. The regular curvature indicates that the model balances sensitivity and specificity evenly. Figure 2d: Activation map on first spatial convolution layer throughout a random positive sample. The top row shows activation maps, where red and blue indicate high and low activation respectively. Bottom row shows original echocardiogram for reference, where blue indicates flow away from ultrasound probe and red indicates towards ultrasound probe. Note the activation on both cardiac flow and structure (white). Figure 2e: instance predictions of negative and positive samples. Red lines indicate positive instance predictions, while white ones are negative (red line thickness indicates magnitude of adjacent positive predictions). Notice the large gaps of negative instance predictions in the negative sample, whereas the positive sample has higher periodicity and frequency. The presence of both positive and negative instance predictions for both samples indicates the model's ability to learn finer features (i.e., frame-wise) when only given video-wise labels.

Keywords

Multiple Instance Learning; Tricuspid Regurgitation; Video Classification

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